

Data for Policy 2020

Fifth International Conference

15 – 17 September 2020
Virtual

Welcome

It is a pleasure to welcome you once again to Data for Policy, which is rapidly becoming the premier global forum for multiple disciplinary and cross-sector discussions around the theories, applications and implications of data science innovation in governance and the public sector.

In partnership with Cambridge University Press, the conference series has also entered into a new open-access peer-reviewed journal venture, Data & Policy, in order to capture and archive scholarly discussions in this fast-growing field. We hope to showcase contributions from conference participants through publications in this journal, particularly via our conference special tracks. In addition, many conference authors have submitted discussion papers to our [Zenodo community](#), and videos of their presentations to our [YouTube channel](#).

Due to the coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic, Data for Policy 2020 is being held virtually. This decision was necessitated not only by uncertainty regarding travel restrictions, but also to protect our delegates' health and safety. Our virtual meeting will fulfill our central purpose as a top international forum by bringing together key stakeholders despite the difficulties we have all encountered. Given the pioneering role of the Data for Policy community, we believe this experience will also enable us to experiment on more innovative and efficient ways to improve our future physical meetings as well.

Beyond practical considerations, we also believe the Data for Policy 2020 conference will be a great opportunity to also assess and review the data science responses to the current global pandemic. The conference will host over 100 speakers from around the world. Themes will be broad-ranging including consideration of data governance and quality, the ethics of data use and data technologies applied to areas such as sustainable development, smart cities and the Covid-19 pandemic.

We will feature three keynote speakers: Professor David Hand's will highlight the importance of data that we don't know in this lecture 'Dark Data'. Professor Alessandro Vespignani will provide insights into large-scale data driven models for infectious disease threats in his lecture 'Computational Epidemiology at the time of Covid-19'. In our final lecture, 'Philosophy and Ethics of Brain-Inspired AI' Professor Yi Zeng will delve into the philosophical foundations of approaches to AI.

Our three plenary sessions will feature an array of panellists from a variety of backgrounds. In the opening plenary, panellists will discuss the relevance of data use for public value. Our partner organisation, Cambridge University Press will host a panel to consider how interactions between data and policy could be produced and shared to achieve impact. In the closing plenary, a panel will debate pertinent issues of inequality.

We look forward to engaging with our community in the virtual mode, with our conference timetable stretching across time zones, from West to East.

Conference Committees

Conference Chairs:

Zeynep Engin – University College London
Jon Crowcroft – University of Cambridge, Alan Turing Institute
Stefaan Verhulst – New York University

International Organisation Committee

Leigh Anderson – University of Washington
Emanuele Baldacci – European Commission
Jon Crowcroft – University of Cambridge, Alan Turing Institute
Zeynep Engin – University College London
Innar Liiv – Tallinn University of Technology, Estonia
Christoph Luetge – Institute of Ethics and AI, ITM, Munchen
H. Scott Matthews – Carnegie Mellon University
Barbara Ubaldi – OECD, Paris
Stefaan Verhulst – New York University

Special Track Chairs:

Leigh Anderson – University of Washington
Jenny Bunn – UCL Information Studies
Sarah Giest – Leiden University
Bilal Gokpinar – UCL School of Management
Daniele Guariso – University of Sussex and The Alan Turing Institute
Omar Guerrero – The Alan Turing Institute and UCL
Elizabeth Lomas – UCL Information Studies
Francesco Mureddu – Lisbon Council
Alison Powell – LSE and the Ada Lovelace Institute
Lorena Rivero del Paso – Global Initiative for Fiscal Transparency
Barbara Ubaldi – OECD, Paris
Stefaan Verhulst – The GovLab, NYU
Benjamin Welby – OECD, France
Masaru Yarime – Hong Kong University of Science and Technology, Hong Kong; UCL STEaPP, UK; and The University of Tokyo, Japan
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Helen Margetts – University of Oxford; The Alan Turing Institute
Beth Noveck – New York University
Alan Penn – University College London

Rob Procter – University of Warwick; The Alan Turing Institute
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Michael Veale – University College London
Andrew Young – New York University
Louisa Zanoun – UK Science and Innovation Network

Conference Programme (September 15th – 17th)

Starting 15th September 2020, London time

13:00 – 13:15 **Opening Remarks**

Welcome to the Conference - Zeynep Engin, Founder of Data for Policy

Arrangements for the Conference – Emily Gardner, Data for Policy Community Manager

13:15 – 14:15 **Opening Plenary Panel**

Chair: Barbara **Ubaldi**, OECD

Speakers:

Jeffrey **Schlagenhauf**, Deputy Secretary-General OECD

Sir Peter **Gluckmann**, Former Chief Scientific Advisor, New Zealand

Zuena **Aziz**, Chief Coordinator for Sustainable Development Goals Affairs in the Prime Minister's Office, Bangladesh

Jeanine **Vos**, Head of SDG Accelerator, GSMA

14:15 – 15:00 **Session 1**

Standard Track: *Data, Governance and Policy I*

Chair: Emanuele **Baldacci**, European Commission

[9] “*Google Economics: Data – Complex Models – well-informed Policy Making*”; Doyne **Farmer**, University of Oxford, Claire **Connelly** and Carla **Coburger**, Rebuilding Macroeconomics, National Institute of Economic and Social Research

[74] “*Knowledge Politics in the Smart City*”; Timea **Nochta**, Noura **Wahby** and Jennifer **Schooling**, University of Cambridge

[38] “*Comparing contexts of evidence dissemination: The effect of crisis characteristics on the politicisation of expert knowledge*”; Igor **Tkalec** and Gaby **Umbach**, European University Institute

[106] “*Smart Rural: The Open Data Gap*”; Johanna **Walker**, University of Southampton; Gefion **Thuermer**, King's College London, Elena **Simperl**, King's College London, and Leslie **Carr**, University of Southampton

[136] “*Data-Driven Management of Outlier Events and their Effects on Agricultural Economics and Policy*”; Feras **Batarseh**, George Mason University, Munisamy **Gopinath**, University of Georgia and Ruixin **Yang**, George Mason University

15:00 – 15:15 **Short Break**

15:15 – 16:00 **Session 2**

Special Track: *Data Governance in the Public Interest*

Chair: Alison **Powell**, LSE and JUST AI Network / the Ada Lovelace Institute

[54] “*Digital Economy Act 2017, Research Strand: De-Identified Public Authority Data for Public Good Research*”; Lily **O’Flynn** and Simon **Whitworth**, UK Statistics Authority

[66] “*Risk to Collaboration: Assessing the risks of Cross-border Open Data Sharing by Civil Society Organizations in the Lower-Mekong Region*”; Arthur Glenn **Maail**, World Wide Web Foundation, Indonesia and Dhanaraj **Thakur**, Center for Democracy and Technology, USA

[81] “*Imagining Municipalities as Data Fiduciaries*”; Craig **Campbell**, Oxford Internet Institute

[92] “*Accessing privately held data to foster the public interest: Mapping public/private sector relations in twelve European cities*”; Marina **Micheli**, Joint Research Commission, European Commission

[102] “*Unravelling the contact tracing apps’ saga: Lessons to create synergies between decentralised and centralised data governance*”; Maria **Savona**, University of Sussex

16:00 – 16:45 **Session 3**

Special Panel: *Data, analytics and digital transformation in the private sector*

Chairs: Bilal **Gokpinar** and Steve **Yoo**, UCL School of Management

Jonathan **Bell**, Chief Investment Officer, Cape Ann Asset Management

Vishal **Dixit**, Strategy and Wholesale Director, Vodafone

John **Lee**, Director, KPMG Lighthouse Center of Excellence for AI

16:45 – 17:00 **Short Break**

17:00 – 17:50 **Keynote Lecture 1**

“Dark Data”

David **Hand**, Imperial College

Chair: Innar **Liiv**, Tallinn University of Technology, Estonia

17:50 – 18:35 **Session 4**

Special Track: *‘For good measure’: The challenges of quantifying complex problems for policymaking I -*

Special Session: *“The co-production of value from data by users and producers”*

Chair: Sarah **Giest**, Leiden University

Co-Chair: Felix **Ritchie**, University of the West of England

[95a] *“Introduction: Co-production and the art of integrating skillsets”*; Felix **Ritchie**, University of the West of England, James **Tierney** and Rachel **Mullis**, Office for National Statistics, UK

[95b] *“Quality assurance: exploiting different ways of looking at data”*; Arusha **McKenzie** and Damian **Whittard**, University of the West of England

[95c] *“Linking: applying theory to practice in an institutional setting”*; John **Forth**, City University, and Van **Phan**, University of the West of England

[95d] *“Identifying use value: developing a research strategy”*; Alex Bryson, **UCL**, and Lucy Stokes, **NIESR**

18:35 – 19:45 **Long Break**

19:45 – 20:30 **Session 5**

Special Track: *Re-using data to address COVID-19 and Pandemics*

Chair: Stefaan **Verhulst**, The GovLab, NYU

[70] *“Real-Time Mobility Analysis Through Google Maps”*; Ingmar **Weber**, Nan **Tang**, Soon-Gyo **Jung**, Rade **Stanojevic**, Noora **Al-Emadi** and Ji **Lucas**, Qatar Computing Research Institute

[58] *“COVID-19 Mobile App Accountability Project”*; Quentin **Palfrey**, International Digital Accountability Council

[109] “*The strategic relevance of data governance for open government data: lessons from COVID-19*”; Felipe **Gonzalez-Zapata**, Jacob Arturo **Rivera Pérez**, Cecilia **Emilsson** and Lucia **Chauvet**, OECD

20:30 – 21:20

Session 6

Special Track: *Data Quality and Development Policy*

Chair: C. Leigh Anderson, University of Washington

[128] “*Assessing Progress towards Development Goals: Data Source Trade-offs and Complementarities*”; C. Leigh **Anderson**, Conor **Hennessey**, Carly **Schmidt** and Andrew **Tomes**, University of Washington

[103] “*Working out the kinks: Challenges in evaluating the global gender equality goals and indicators*”; Sara Rose **Taylor**, Framework Convention Alliance, Canada

[60] “*Transparency and Accountability in Research Funding Bodies: An Open Data Lacuna in Science Policy*”; Kalpana **Shankar**, Lai **Ma** and Junwen **Luo**, University College Dublin

[114] “*Comparing Measures of Internet Governance: Analyzing the trade-offs between Remote Measurement and Expert Analysis*”; Terry **Fletcher** and Andria **Hayes-Birchler**, Millenium Challenge Corporation, USA

[123] “*Design for policy in data for policy practices. Exploring potential convergences for policy innovation*”; Francesco **Leoni**, Politecnico di Milano

21:20

Day Break

09:00 – 09:45

Session 7

Special Track: *Data Governance for Innovation for Sustainable Smart Cities: Opportunities and Challenges in Public Policy and Institutional Design I*

Chair: Masaru **Yarime**, Hong Kong University of Science and Technology, Hong Kong; UCL STEaPP, UK; and The University of Tokyo, Japan

[31] “*The Role of Data in Sustainability Assessment of Urban Mobility Policies*”; Xu **Liu** and Marc **Dijk**, Maastricht University

[49] “*Increasing Resilience toward COVID-19 via Risk Mapping: Co-creation of Data for Stakeholder Engagement in Hong Kong*”; Veronica **Li** and Masaru **Yarime**, Hong Kong University of Science and Technology

[63] “*Data-driven Urban Systems for Sustainable Smart City Development*”; Patrycja-Jadwiga **Sankowska**, ModelCity+ and Junqing **Tang**, University of Cambridge

[96] “*Simulation Governance: Smart City Digital Twin as Data Platform*”; Gleb **Papyshev**, Hong Kong University of Science and Technology

09:00 – 10:30

Session 8

Special Track: *Documenting Data and Data Science: Surfacing Data Processes and Practices*

Chairs: Jenny Bunn and Elizabeth Lomas, UCL

[29] “*Exploring Data Friction: Recommendations for Cultural Heritage and Digital Humanities*”; Kristen **Schuster**, King’s College London and Vanessa **Reyes**, Southern Florida University

[101] “*Social media adoption in government – A provocation on disrupting practices and policy alternatives*”; Elizabeth **Shaffer**, University of British Columbia

[138] “*Recording Machine Learning Algorithmic Development in the UK’s Private Sector*”; Josie **Sommer**, UCL

[139] “*Anonymity in an epidemic: citizen tracking, recording and future privacy implications*”; Inez **McGregor**, UCL

[130] “*How to Machine-Extract Archival Data: Creating Archival-Minded Computational Models*”; Bethany **Anderson**, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

10:30 – 10:45

Short Break

10:45 – 11:30

Session 9

Standard Track: *Governance Technologies (GovTech)*

Chair: Innar **Liiv**, Tallinn University of Technology, Estonia

[23] “*Local Regulation of Global Digital Platforms; How AI Algorithms Change the Borders in the Age of Data*”; Imad Al-Din **Payande**, Sharif Governance Think Tank, Iran, Ahmad **Ronaghikhameneh**, Polytechnic University of Milan and Hossein **Mirzapour**, Sharif Policy Research Institute and University of Montreal

[43] “*Developing Machine Learning Technique for Measuring Central Bank Credibility*”; Okiriza **Wibisono**, Alvin Andhika **Zulen** and Angraini **Widjanarti**, Bank Indonesia

[122] “*Reducing corruption in public procurement using machine learning*”; Maria Ines **Aran**, Instituto tecnologico de Buenos Aires, João **Carabetta**, Universidade Estadual de Campinas, Jian **Wen**, University of Cambridge, Anna **Julià-Verdaguer**, Eurecat, Centre Tecnològic de Catalunya, Pablo **Rosado**, Joshua **Sidgwick**, Sebastian **Vollmer**, The Alan Turing Institute, and Rayid **Ghani**, Carnegie Mellon University

[108] “*Is One Plus One Always Two? Insuring Longevity Risk While Having Multiple Savings Accounts*”; Abigail **Hurwitz** and Orly **Sade**, The Hebrew University of Jerusalem

[71] *“Residential burglary risk population modelling: An interactive policy tool to shape the targeting of burglary reduction initiatives via an enhanced analysis of residential burglary rates at the neighbourhood level”*; James **Hunter**, Bethany **Ward**, Andromachi **Tseloni**, Nottingham Trent University and Ken **Pease**, University of Derby

11:30 – 12:15 **Session 10**

Special Track: *Harnessing Data and Science to Achieve the Sustainable Development Goals*

Chair: Lorena **Rivero del Paso**, Global Initiative for Fiscal Transparency

[17] *“Non-linear interlinkages and key objectives amongst the Paris Agreement and the Sustainable Development Goals”*; Felix **Laumann**, Imperial College, Julius **von Kugelgen**, Max Planck Institute for Intelligent Systems, Germany, and Mauricio **Barahona**, Imperial College

[32] *“Applying Epidemiological Thinking to Assess Anti-Trafficking Interventions in the Thai Garment Industry”*; Michael **Gallo**, United Nations University Institute in Macau, Renata **Konrad**, Worcester Polytechnic Institute, USA and Hannah **Thinyane**, United Nations University Institute in Macau

[62] *“Budgeting for SDGs: A Data-driven Approach”*; Daniele **Guariso**, University of Sussex, Omar **Guerrero**, UCL and The Alan Turing Institute and Gonzalo **Castañeda**, Centro de Investigación y Docencia Económicas

[76] *“Assessing the Feasibility of the SDGs: Large A Global Analysis of Policy Priorities and Their Budgets”*; Omar **Guerrero**, UCL and The Alan Turing Institute and Gonzalo **Castañeda**, Centro de Investigación y Docencia Económicas

[88] *“Using machine learning methods to better understand the complexities of the national prevalence of modern slavery”*; Rosa **Lavelle-Hill**, Anjali **Mazumder**, The Alan Turing Institute, James **Goulding** and Gavin **Smith**, University of Nottingham

[93] *“Policy Priority Inference: A Computational Method for the Analysis of Sustainable Development”*; Gonzalo **Castañeda**, Centro de Investigación y Docencia Económicas and Omar **Guerrero**, UCL and The Alan Turing Institute

12:15 – 13:45 - **Long Break**

13:45 – 14:30 **Session 11**

Standard Track: *Trust, Privacy, Ethics & Law*

Chair: John **Pullinger**, President of the International Association for Official Statistics

[52] *“Trust, Security & Public Interest: Striking the Balance. Public attitudes towards the sharing and linking of administrative data for research”*; Elizabeth **Waind**, Administrative Data Research UK

[84] *"Data ethics in practice: challenges and opportunities for data ethics in the public sector"*; Natalia **Domagala**, Department for Digital, Culture, Media and Sport, UK

[86] *"The Role of Consumer Trust and Policy Tensions in the European Commission's Data and AI Strategy"*; Jose Tomas **Llanos** and Madeline **Carr**, UCL

[99] *"Paternalism in the governance of artificial intelligence and automated decision-making in the United Kingdom"*; Archie **Drake** and Perry **Keller**, King's College London

[75] *"Data Protection for the Common Good: Developing a framework for a data protection-focused data commons"*; Janis **Wong**, Tristan **Henderson** and Kirstie **Ball**, University of St Andrews

14:30 – 15:15 Session 12

Special Track: *Data technologies and governance frameworks used for gathering, storing, managing, processing, analyzing and sharing data in the public administrations*

Chairs: Francesco **Mureddu**, Lisbon Council and Stefaan **Verhulst**, The GovLab, NYU

[50] *"Establishing a data ecosystem to support the use of telecom data to inform COVID-19 response efforts"*; Ayumi **Arai**, Apichon **Witayangkurn**, Hiroshi **Kanasugi**, Ryosuke **Shibasaki** and Satoshi **Ueyama**, University of Tokyo

[56] *"How Data Governance Technologies Can Democratize Data Sharing for Community Well-being"*; Daniel **Wu**, Immuta, US, Stefaan **Verhulst**, The GovLab, NYU, Alex **Pentland**, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Thiago **Avila**, Universidade Federal de Alagoas, Abhishek **Gupta**, Microsoft and Montreal AI Ethics Institute and Kelsey **Finch**, Future of Privacy Forum, USA

[115] *"Disposable Yet Official Identities (DYOI) for Privacy-Preserving System Design - The case of COVID-19 digital document verification and credential-based access control in ad hoc outdoor and indoor settings (and beyond)"*; Petros **Kavassalis**, Nikos **Triantafyllou**, University of the Aegean, Panagiotis **Georgakopoulos**, Athens University of Economics and Business, Antonis **Stasis** and Rob **van Kranenburg**, University of the Aegean

[126] *"Data Exchange or Verifiable Claims? Different paradigms to address data sharing challenges and to implement modern data access"*; Joao Rodrigues **Frade**, European Commission

15:15 – 15:30 Short Break

15:30 – 16:20 Data & Policy Plenary Panel

"How can Interactions Between Data and Policy be Produced, Shared and Achieve Impact?"

Organiser: Andrew **Hyde**, Cambridge University Press

Chair: Matthew **Day**, Cambridge University Press

Speakers:

Jean Claude **Burgelman**, Vrije University Brussels; former Head of Unit Open Data Policies and Science Cloud DG RTD, European Commission

Samia **Melhem**, Global Lead on Digital Capabilities, Digital Development Practice, World Bank

Martijn **Poel**, Senior Policy Official, Dutch Ministry of Education, Culture and Science

16:20 – 17:05 **Session 13**

Special Session (Alan Turing Institute): *Opportunities and Challenges for Data-Driven Research in Response to the COVID-19 Crisis*

Chair: Florian **Ostmann**, The Alan Turing Institute

[77a] “*Responsible research and innovation practices for rapid-response data science in the context of COVID-19*”; David **Leslie** and Christopher **Burr**, The Alan Turing Institute

[77b] “*The promise and pitfalls of measuring the impact of COVID-19-related policy interventions*”; Helen **Margetts** and Cosmina **Dorobantu**, The Alan Turing Institute

[77c] “*Understanding and countering vulnerability to health-related misinformation during COVID-19*”; Bertram **Vidgen**, The Alan Turing Institute

17:05 - 18:30 **Long Break**

18:30 – 19:20 **Keynote Lecture 2**

‘Computational Epidemiology at the time of Covid-19’

Alessandro **Vespignani**, Northeastern University

Chair: Stefaan **Verhulst**, The GovLab, NYU

19:20 – 20:05 **Session 14**

Special Panel: “*Contemporary challenges in science and policy*”

Chair: C. Leigh Anderson, University of Washington

[125a] Jaron **Porciello**, Cornell University, Ceres2030: Sustainable Solutions to End Hunger

[125b] Todd **Rosenstock**, ICRAF, Evidence for Resilient Agriculture (ERA)

[125c] Trevor **Butterworth**, Sense about Science USA and Trinity College Dublin

[125d] Gracian **Chimwaza**, Information Training and Outreach Centre for Africa

[125e] Chris **Surridge**, Springer-Nature

[125f] Stanley **Wood**, The Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation

20:05 Day Break

09:00 – 09:45 Session 15

Special Track: *Data Governance in the Public Interest -*

Special Panel: *“Brave New Worlds? Ethics in Theory and Practice in Public Data Provision”*

Chair: Alison **Powell**, LSE and JUST AI Network / the Ada Lovelace Institute

[98a] *“Reconsidering the ‘Public/Private’ Divide in Data Governance: Legal Realities and Ethical Implications”*; Stergios **Aidinlis**, Centre for Socio-Legal Studies, University of Oxford;

[98b] *“Towards a New Ethical Approach to Data Governance: Challenges and Potentialities”*; Francesco **Tava**, Department of Health and Social Sciences; University of the West of England

[98c] *“Risk, Precedents and Sand: Introducing Novelty into Practice in the Public Sector”*; Felix **Ritchie**, Bristol Business School, University of the West of England

[98d] *“Implementing Ethical Models in Low Income Countries”*; Elizabeth **Green**, Bristol Business School, University of the West of England

09:45 – 10:30 Session 16

Special Track: *Data Governance for Innovation for Sustainable Smart Cities: Opportunities and Challenges in Public Policy and Institutional Design II*

Chair: Masaru **Yarime**, Hong Kong University of Science and Technology, Hong Kong; UCL STEaPP, UK; and The University of Tokyo, Japan.

[67] *“Engaging Citizens in Data Governance for Net Zero Precincts”*; Darren **Sharp**, Sarah **Goodwin**, Misita **Anwar**, Monash University, and Lyn **Bartram**, Simon Fraser University

[79] *“The Critical Role of Social Acceptance of Publics in Smart City Data-Driven Innovation: The Case of Smart Lamp Post Project in Hong Kong”*; Wilson **Wong** and Sylvia **Ying He**, The Chinese University of Hong Kong

[110] “A Collaborative Governance Mechanism Aiming at the Low Application Rate of the Government Data Platform in Smart City Contexts — Illustrated by Shenzhen Case”; Siqi **Xie**, Ning **Luo** and Masaru **Yarime**, Hong Kong University of Science and Technology

10:30 – 10:45 **Short Break**

10:45 – 11:30 **Session 17**

Special Session (OECD): “Towards a new data-driven service design and delivery model?”

Chair: Barbara **Ubaldi**

Benjamin **Welby**, OECD – on OECD data and service design/delivery

Tom **Wynne-Morgan**, Homes England/Ministry of Housing, Communities and Local Government - on data and homelessness

Tom **Nixon**, Faculty AI – on data in AI for public services

Sungjoo **Son**, Director of Digital Government Cooperation Division at the Ministry of the Interior and Safety, Korea

11:30 – 12:15 **Session 18**

Standard Track: *Data, Governance and Policy II*

Chair: H. Scott **Matthews**, Carnegie Mellon University

[30] “Laying the Foundation for Effective Partnerships: Examining Data Sharing Agreements”; Hayden **Dahmm** and Jessica **Espey**, UNSDSN-TRENDS

[42] “Principles for data governance at INRAE”; Gilles **Aumont**, Michael **Chelle**, Esther **Dzale-Yeumo**,

Odile **Hologne**, Olivier **Philippe**, Hadi **Quesneville** and Stéphanie **Rennes**, INRAE, France

[100] “Principles for revenue models and sustainability of a ‘good steward’”; Aditi **Ramesh** and Astha **Kapoor**, Aapti Institute, India

[117] “Stand Away from The Platform: The Negative Aspects of The Platform and the use of Data Trusts”; David **Jamieson**, Rob **Wilson**, Northumbria University and Mike **Martin**, Newcastle Business School

[36] “Fostering Trustworthy Data Sharing: Establishing Data Foundations in Practice”; Sophie **Stalla-Bourdillon**, Laura **Carmichael**, University of Southampton and Alexis **Wintour**, Lapin Limited, Jersey

12:15 – 13:15 **Long Break**

13:15 – 14:05 **Keynote Lecture 3**

“Philosophy and Ethics of Brain-inspired AI”

Speaker: Yi **Zeng**, Beijing Academy

Chair: Christoph **Lütge**, Institute of Ethics and AI, ITM, Munich

14:05 – 14:50 **Session 19**

Special Track: *‘For good measure’: The challenges of quantifying complex problems for policymaking II*

Chair: Sarah **Giest**, Leiden University

[69] *“Why Policymakers Don’t Use Your Data”*; Mitzi **Bolton**, Monash University

[112] *“A hybrid methodology for data-driven policy making”*; Anne Fleur **Van Veenstra**, TNO, Netherlands

[83] *“The Data First programme and challenges of quantifying complex problems for justice research”*; Robin **Linacre**, Kylie **Hill**, Amy **Summerfield**, Ministry of Justice and Andromachi **Tseloni**, Ministry of Justice and Nottingham Trent University

[97] *“Blockchains meet GovTech: Governance and Regulatory Mechanisms for the Public Interest”*; Claudio **Lombardi**, KIMEP, Kazakhstan, Marios **Isaakidis** and Saira **Mian**, UCL

[120] *“Automated Performance Systems and Enforceability of Contracts: The Case of Amazon Web Services and Microsoft Azure”*; Golnaz **Jafari**, University of Lucerne and Benedikt **Schuppli**, Université Paris II

14:50 – 15:05 **Short Break**

15:05 – 15:50 **Session 20**

Standard Track: *Data Processing and Knowledge Generation*

Chair: Jon **Crowcroft**, University of Cambridge and the Alan Turing Institute

[35] *“The accuracy vs. interpretability trade-off in Fraud Detection Analytics”*; Anna **Nesvijevskaia**, Quinten and Laboratoire DICEN Ile de France, Sophie **Ouillade**, Pauline **Guilmin**, Quinten and Jean-Daniel **Zucker**, Sorbonne University

[64] *“Using Open Data to Monitor the Status of a Metropolitan Area: the case of the*

metropolitan area of Turin"; Filippo **Candela** and Paolo **Mulassano**,
Compagnia di San Paolo Foundation, Italy

[65] *"The case for computationally forecasting the evolving interactions between CJEU Judgements and EU legal acts to anticipate policy adoption"*; Pedro V **Hernandez Serrano** and Laura **Robinson**, Institute of Data Science at Maastricht University

[94] *"Uncovering policy designs from legal texts"*; Lynn H. **Kaack** and Sebastian **Sewerin**,
ETH Zurich

[87] *"A New Approach to Impact Case Study Analytics"*; Jiajie **Zhang**, Paul **Watson** and
Barry **Hodgson**, Newcastle University

15:50 – 16:50 Closing Plenary Panel

Chair: C. Leigh Anderson, University of Washington

Speakers:

Katie **Atkinson**, Dean of Electrical Engineering, Electronics, and Computer Science,
University of Liverpool

Kamau **Bobb**, Global Lead, Diversity Strategy and Research at Google

Torbjörn **Fredriksson**, Head of ICT Analysis Section of the Division on Technology and
Logistics, UN Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD)

Himanshu **Nagpal**, Deputy Director Financial Services for the Poor, Bill & Melinda Gates
Foundation

16:50 – 17:00 Closing Remarks

Stefaan Verhulst, The GovLab

Zeynep Engin, Founder of Data for Policy

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